

PLAN'EAT

Ethics requirements

Deliverable D7.4

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DELIVERABLE PLAN'EAT – D7.4

Ethics requirements

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R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	X
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	
DMP	Data management plan	
ETHICS	Deliverables related to ethics issues.	
SECURITY	Deliverables related to security issues	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.	

Dissemination level		
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SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
CI	Classified, EU RESTRICTED, CONFIDENTIAL or SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444	

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Executive summary

D7.4 Ethics Requirements presents the ethical obligations to safeguard the consent procedures of the consortium of PLAN'EAT project partners and stakeholders.

PLAN'EAT activities include the performance of 9 Living Labs (LLs), intervention studies involving human participants that will produce newly generated original data (primary data) in a pan-EU network. In PLAN'EAT newly generated data (primary data) will be coupled with re-used data (secondary data) to create a comprehensive and large database on the dietary pattern (consumption, composition, dietary behaviors) and food environment. The goal of this deliverable is to describe the ethical requirements and obligations of the PLAN'EAT project. In order to perform the planned activities, each LL must request approval for the study from its local/national ethical committees. Local/National Ethical Committees will ensure the compliance of the studies involving human data collection with relevant regulations. Participants will be recruited, on a voluntary basis and after having expressed full informed consent, in the first year of the project and consulted all along its lifetime. In 3 LLs human biological samples (urine, blood, etc.) will be collected. No tissue and cells will be collected in the activities involving humans in the PLAN'EAT project. Data collected in the PLAN'EAT project, either newly generated or reused, will be used for an AI approach to propose personalized meal plans. As it will mainly consist in analyzing data and providing recommendations, it does not raise concerns regarding human rights, or personal aspects, and will not have any negative impacts. In the present deliverable, an analysis of the AI system development and use of PLAN'EAT is provided.

1. Introduction

As a part of Work Package 7, the present deliverable 7.4 concerns the ethical requirements and obligations of the PLAN'EAT project. The ethics requirements of PLAN'EAT are related to the newly generated data in the framework of field activities namely the 9 Living Labs (LLs) that PLAN'EAT will co-create to perform intervention studies and produce original data in a pan-EU network. Besides the LLs, PLAN'EAT will use other data collected for different purposes that will be reanalyzed for the scope of the PLAN'EAT project. These re-used sets of data will be received by the PLAN'EAT responsible beneficiaries in an anonymous form and, in case of the presence of personal data, they are never traceable nor attributable to the person of origin.

Data collected in the PLAN'EAT project, either newly generated or reused, will be used for an Artificial Intelligence approach to propose personalized meal plans. As it will mainly consist in analyzing data and providing some recommendations, it does not raise concerns regarding human rights, or personal aspects, and will not have any negative impacts. As outlined in the D7.1 "*Data Management Plan*", the data collected in the PLAN'EAT project aligns with the FAIR principles—Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability— thereby enhancing its value and utility for the research community and beyond.

The present deliverable (D7.4) should be read in line with the D7.1 on the Data Management Plan (DMP). In addition to that, the ethical requirements and obligations of the PLAN'EAT project are addressed in the framework of Work Package 8 in D8.1 on the Procedure to recruit research participants, D8.2 on the use of Human cells, tissue, and biological samples collection, D8.3 on Personal data processing and safeguard. Finally in D8.4 on the Human rights impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI), the criticism of the algorithm design and outcomes of the PLAN'EAT project and the ethics risks and the mitigation measures related to the AI are examined. The ethics requirements and obligations of PLAN'EAT will be included and further evaluated during the project activities in the Ethics assessments that the PLAN'EAT Ethic Advisory will perform at the end of each reporting period (D8.6, D8.7, D8.8).

1.1 The generated data - Living Labs in PLAN'EAT project

PLAN'EAT project activities include the creation and implementation of 9 LLs and 1 Policy Lab for which a joint approach and methodological tools will be set up and completed at M6 (D5.1 -Toolbox of methodologies and tools to set and run a living lab). The LLs of PLAN'EAT will create the newly generated datasets for the project. The LLs represent a participatory, systemic, and multi-actor approach, operating as close as possible to local stakeholders and target population groups. According to the Grant Agreement (GA), "*each LL will include all types of local food system actors. Each LL will count 10 to 20 active members, that will be regularly consulted, and each citizen panel/cohort/patient group will gather between 60 and 200 consumers*". In addition to that, an EU policy lab gathering up to 20 European policymakers will also be held in Brussels (WP5). The EU Policy LL has characteristics not implying actions with ethical implications and will not be considered in the other paragraphs of the present deliverable.

Table 1 reports a synthesis of the PLAN'EAT LLs with information relevant to ethics requirements and obligations. Free-living populations will be the target groups of 7 LLs, amongst which 4 LLs will target children. In 3 LLs, biological samples will be collected with the consequent requirement of tailored documentation that will be submitted in D2.3 and D2.4 at M8; one of the mentioned clinical LLs will involve children. The EU Policy Lab has characteristics not implying actions in terms of ethical procedures for participant recruitment and will not be considered in the other paragraphs of the present deliverable.

Table 1: Living Labs main characteristics

Living Lab (LL)	Target group	Setting	Children and/or adults unable to give informed consent
TUM Bayern (DE)	Obese and overweight children and adolescents from a cohort in Germany (Age: 10-20)	Clinical	Yes
INRAE Auvergne Rhone Alpes (FR)	Healthy children and adolescents, middle and high SES, urban and rural (Age: 6-15)	School	Yes
UCD Dublin (IE)	Healthy young adults – University students, all SES (Age: 18-30)	University Campus	No
SLU Sweden (SE)	Healthy toddlers, middle and high SES (Age: <6)	Pre-school and household	Yes
JU – Poland (PL)	Healthy children and adolescents, low SES (Age: 1-16)	Household and kindergarten	Yes
ESSRG Budapest (HU)	Healthy young adults with low SES (Age: 20-30)	Citizen Community	No
UOC Catalonia (ES)	Healthy adults from middle age to elderly, low SES, (Age: 40-85)	Citizen Community	No
UNIBO Bologna - Pilastro (IT)	Diabetic adults from low SES (low income/ rural/ immigrants), (Age: 18-70).	Clinical	No
HUA Attica (EL)	Elderly people, NCDs, all SES (Age: > 60)	Free-living population	No
EU Policy EPHA Brussels (BE)	Policy Lab focusing on policymaking and gathering policymakers from the relevant EU Institutions, the European Parliament, the European Council, the European Economic and Social Committee, and the European civil society.	N/A	N/A

1.2 The re-used data in the PLAN'EAT project

In the framework of PLAN'EAT, secondary data (re-used data) on the dietary pattern (consumption, composition, dietary behaviors) and food environment in the 11 countries and the 12 pre-selected target groups will be collected (WP1). WP2 aimed to identify key leverage points for behavior change within LLs' food systems, thus environmental, socio-economic, and health secondary data will be further collected and coupled with data collected in WP1. In WP3, the database resulting from WP1 and WP2 will be further used to (1) identify and understand the environmental, social, and health impacts of predominant dietary patterns (as relevant for different target groups); (2) measure, analyze, and compare the true costs of selected dietary patterns highlighting and evaluating the positive and negative externalities thereof; and (3) inform the desired directionality of the transition process and associated behavioral change. Based on the outcomes of WP2 and WP3, WP4 will aim at developing a coherent mix of interventions, including methodologies, tools, and materials, that will allow policymakers and other food system actors across Europe to steer a transition toward healthier and more sustainable dietary behavior. All interventions will be designed and tested through co-creation methods in the living labs (WP5).

Data collected in the PLAN'EAT project, either newly generated or reused, will be used for an AI approach to propose personalized meal plans. As it will mainly consist in analyzing data and providing recommendations,

it does not raise concerns regarding human rights, or personal aspects, and will not have any negative impacts. In the present deliverable, an analysis of the AI system development and use of PLAN'EAT is provided.

2. The ethics requirements of the activities involving human people in PLAN'EAT

To accomplish the ethics requirements and obligation of activities involving the human people of PLAN'EAT, a series of documents will be submitted as a deliverable before the start of the relevant activities. As the recruitment of participants will not start at the same time for all LLs, an update of the status of documents will be provided in the deliverables related to the ethics assessment (e.g. D8.6 - Ethic advisor report due at M18) and in the first technical report of the project (Technical Report, Part B – M18).

2.1 The procedure and criteria to identify/recruit research participants

The LLs of PLAN'EAT will focus on a broad range of population groups, varying according to age, culture, health, and socio-economic status. In consideration of the differences between the LLs' target groups, the present paragraph will summarise the procedure and criteria that each LL is going to put in place to perform the activities in accordance with the rules of the 1975 Declaration of Helsinki, revised in 2013¹. In addition, the procedure for participants to sign a policy privacy and consent form for collecting and processing personal data in advance, according to the National Data Protection Law in line with the European Commission General Data Protection Regulation (679/2016) is reported.

In order to perform the planned activities, each LL must request approval for the study from its local/national ethical committees. Local/National Ethical Committees will ensure the compliance of the studies involving human data collection with relevant regulations. In addition to that, the publication of results in peer-reviewed journals often requires the approval of an ethical board also for studies that do not involve biological sample collection (e.g., using fecal samples, voided urine, blood, etc.), laboratory assessment, induced lifestyle changes or, dietary intake modifications.

In activities involving human people of PLAN'EAT, participants will be recruited, on a voluntary basis and after having expressed full informed consent, in the first year of the project and consulted all through its lifetime. In synthesis, all subject participants to PLAN'EAT LLs provide written consent before participating in the studies and will be free to withdraw from the studies at any time without providing a reason for withdrawal. A copy of both the informed consent form and the subject information sheet is provided to the volunteers participating in the study. Paper archives of these documents will be properly stored, as detailed in D8.3. Subjects will be provided with their data at the end of the study. The protocols for human studies will be submitted to the local/national Ethical Committee for approval before the recruitment of subjects. All clinical procedures will be carried out by experienced medical personnel.

In Table 2, the status of requests (as of 28 February 2023, M6 due date for present deliverable) to national ethical committees for each LL is reported. An update of Table 2 showing the achievement of the approval for all LLs is reported in the technical report (part B) delivered at M18 (First Reporting Period).

¹ <https://www.wma.net/what-we-do/medical-ethics/declaration-of-helsinki/>, accessed on 30 January 2023

Table 2: Status of requests for approval to local/national ethical committees			
Living Lab (LL)	Request for approval	Timing for achieving the approval	N° of the local/national authorization
TUM Bayern (DE)	Yes	Jan 2023	2022-662-S-KK Ethics Committee of the Technical University of Munich
INRAE Auvergne Rhone Alpes (FR)	Yes	February 2023	Awaiting the response from the ethics committee in February
UCD Dublin (IE)	Yes	March 2023	See Technical Report, Part B (M18)
SLU Sweden (SE)	Yes	Awaiting national ethics approval	See Technical Report, Part B (M18)
JU – Poland (PL)	Yes	Achieved on October 2022 (university ethics committee)	Philosophy Department JU Ethics Committee Decision no: 221.0032.12.2022
ESSRG Budapest (HU)	Yes	In progress	See Technical Report, Part B (M18)
UOC Catalonia (ES)	Yes	Achieved on September 2022 (university ethics committee)	CE22- PR17 Ethics Committee of the UOC
UNIBO Bologna - Pilastro (IT)	Yes	April 2023	See Technical Report, Part B (M18)
HUA Attica (EL)	Yes	Achieved in November 2022 (university ethics committee)	42/09.11.2022

Details on the procedures and criteria to identify/recruit research participants are reported in D8.1. In synthesis, the documents related to these procedures to be submitted as deliverables before the start of the relevant activities will be:

- The procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participants.
- The informed consent procedures will be implemented for the research participants and concerning data processing.
- The English version of the templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets covering the voluntary participation and data protection issues (in language and terms intelligible to the participants, including DPO contact details for host institutions required to appoint a DPO under the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679) and the version in local/national language that will be kept on file by the responsible beneficiaries.
- For children and/or adults unable to give informed consent involved, details on how the consent of the legal representatives (and assent of the research participant, when applicable).
- Clarification of whether invasive physical procedures will be used, and, if so, details on the risks involved and the measures that will be taken to minimize risk and possible pain.
- Detailed information on the incidental/unexpected findings policy (including the disclosure policy in case of unexpected findings).
- Copies of opinions/approvals by ethics committees and/or competent authorities for the research with humans will be kept on file and provided upon request.

At the time of publication of the present deliverable (M6), the status of the provision of the above-mentioned documents could be summarized as follows:

- All the LLs responsible started the procedure for ethical clearance requests, 4 out of 9 got the approval; the remaining approvals were achieved before the starting of the activities and reported in Table 20 of the first Technical Report (Part B) provided at M18. Copies of opinions/approvals by ethics committees and/or competent authorities for the research with humans were achieved before the start of the relevant activities, kept on file, and could be provided upon request.

- Informed consent as well as information sheets will stress the voluntary nature of the participation in the actions and the possibility of withdrawing from the activities at any time and for any reason. Informed consent and information sheets were provided in local language and English and reported as an annex in D8.1.
- Compliance with data protection rules and regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 and any other applicable national legislations, will be ensured by each host institution, with regard to the obligations applicable to the processing of personal data performed by such institution.

2.2 The procedure and criteria for human cells, tissue and biological sample collection and management

Table 3 reports a synthesis of the PLAN'EAT LLs characteristics, the occurrence, and typologies of biological sample collection. Subjects involved in PLAN'EAT project activities are volunteers and the interventions carrying out are focused on behavioral changes advising participants to include healthy and sustainable foods in their diet. No other clinical or pharmaceutical intervention will be carried out. Human cells and human tissues will not be collected, and other human biological samples will be collected in the framework of the 3 LLs coordinated by TUM, UCD, and UNIBO. Details on biological samples collection of PLAN'EAT are reported in D8.2. The research involving humans in PLAN'EAT fulfills all legal and ethical requirements of the member states where it is going to be carried out. The ethical guidelines accepted by the relevant Ethics Committees are consistent with the Declaration of Helsinki of the World Health Organization, conventions of the Council of Europe on human rights and biomedicine and comply with the rules and regulations of the National Departments of Health or equivalent authorities. The studies proposed in PLAN'EAT are in line with the principles expressed by the UNESCO Declaration on the human genome (especially with respect to Articles 2 and 3 (Human dignity and the human genome), 5, 6, and 7 (Rights of the person concerned), 10, 12 and 13 (Research on the human genome)). Overall, PLAN'EAT research will adhere to the ethic that research on humans and the resulting applications open vast prospects for progress in improving the health of individuals and mankind as a whole, but that such research should fully respect human dignity, freedom, and human rights, as well as the publication of all forms of discrimination based on genetic characteristics.

Living Lab (LL)	Target group	Setting	Human cells	Human tissues	Other human biological samples/Typology
TUM Bayern (DE)	Obese and overweight children and adolescents from a cohort in Germany (Age: 10-20)	Clinical	No	No	Yes Stool samples, Blood
INRAE Auvergne Rhone Alpes (FR)	Healthy children and adolescents, middle and high SES, urban and rural (Age: 6-15)	School	No	No	No
UCD Dublin (IE)	Healthy young adults – University students, all SES (Age: 18-30)	University Campus	No	No	Yes Blood drop sampling by venipuncture and urine sample
SLU Sweden (SE)	Healthy toddlers, middle and high SES (Age: <6)	Pre-school and household	No	No	No

JU – Poland (PL)	Healthy children and adolescents, low SES (Age: 1-16)	Household and kindergarten	No	No	No
ESSRG Budapest (HU)	Healthy young adults with low SES (Age: 20-30)	Citizen Community	No	No	No
UOC Catalonia (ES)	Healthy adults from middle age to elderly, low SES, (Age: 40-85)	Citizen Community	No	No	No
UNIBO Bologna - Pilastro (IT)	Diabetic adults from low SES (low income/ rural/ immigrants), (Age: 18-70).	Clinical	No	No	Yes Capillary blood samples from acupuncture and saliva samples.
HUA Attica (EL)	Elderly people, NCDs, all SES (Age: > 60)	Free-living population	No	No	No

The standard procedures of biological sample collection and the risk minimization measures are concisely described in Table 4. The physical procedures used in PLAN'EAT LLs will include the collection of stool, saliva, and urine sampling which are low-risk, no-painful procedures. However, health and hygiene precautions need to be put in place to minimize potential hazards to participants and research staff. On the other hand, blood collection either by venipuncture or acupuncture, even if is a common procedure, could expose the participants and the staff to possible threats that need to be minimized. All these procedures will be carried out in clinical settings and by qualified healthcare personnel in the framework of normal clinical practices, limiting the possible risks of the interventions. Further details on risk minimization measures, incidental and unexpected findings policies as well as explanations of laboratory biomarkers can be found in D8.1.

Table 4: Details on the procedure of collection of human cells, tissues, and biological samples obtained within the PLAN'EAT project

Living Lab (LL)	Procedures of collection of biological samples	Risk minimization measures
TUM Bayern (DE)	The stool samples will be collected by the adolescents themselves during the first week and in the last week of their stay at the clinic. The blood sample is taken by the Gaißach Clinic trained personnel.	Stool sample collection is a low-risk, non-painful procedure that needs to be carried out with appropriate health and hygiene conditions to minimize potential risks to participants and research staff. Blood sample collection will be carried out in clinical settings with procedures adequate to prevent infections and avoid pain and discomfort of the participants.
UCD Dublin (IE)	Participants will collect a mid-flow urine sample in the morning at home and will bring the urine sample to UCD on ice using a collection kit and instructions that UCD provides to the participant. A phlebotomist will collect a blood sample by venipuncture using clinical needles and sample-specific	Urine sample collection is a low-risk, non-painful procedure with health and hygienic potential risks that will be minimized. Blood sample collection will be carried out in clinical settings with procedures adequate to prevent infections and

	vacutainers (e.g. serum tube) in a clinical room in UCD designed for human intervention studies.	avoid pain and discomfort of the participants.
UNIBO Bologna - Pilastro (IT)	Each patient at the beginning and end of each visit undergoes a blood sampling using a Dried Blood Spot card (DBS): it consists of an acupuncture with a lancing device (the same type as those used for blood glucose measurement); and a saliva sampling (the patient places the salivary swab in his or her mouth by himself or herself). Both withdrawals are performed/assisted by the attending physician after the patient has signed the appropriate informed consent.	Blood sampling for assessment of diabetic disease compensation is already provided by normal follow-up as per normal clinical practice. Regarding study-specific sample collection, blood drop sampling by acupuncture is just as painful as capillary blood glucose sampling (which is routinely done for blood glucose control in patients with diabetes anyway). Saliva sampling is not painful, health and hygienic measures will be followed.

The LLs intervention studies of PLAN'EAT do not involve the use of genetically engineered or modified organisms and thus possess no risk of transmission among species, across species, or to the environment. While we do not anticipate using any infected material, the usual safety procedures will be adhered to when dealing with human blood and urine samples to ensure that there is no risk of transmission to personnel. These safety procedures will be strictly in line with the relevant institutional and national safety codes considering also COVID-19 epidemiological situation. Institutional and national guidelines for handling and disposal of chemicals and other potentially toxic or infective materials will be followed. Thus, no adverse environmental impact is envisaged because of the studies.

At the time of publication of the present deliverable (M6), the status of the provision of the above-mentioned documents could be summarized as follows:

- The LLs of the PLAN'EAT project are concerned with minimal part biological sample collection since the intervention that will be carried out is mainly behavioral with the promotion of consumption of healthy and sustainable foods in the different target groups.
- The human biological samples (urine, blood, etc.) in the LLs of PLAN'EAT will be collected with procedures complying with the legal and ethical requirements of the member states where it is going to be carried out.
- No tissue and cells will be collected in the activities involving humans in the PLAN'EAT project.
- Adequate and timely follow-up of the clinical LLs in which human biological samples are going to be collected will ensure reporting of any critical issues related to the performance of the intervention trial, including biological sample collection.

2.3 Procedures and criteria for personal data processing and safeguard

Participants will be recruited, on a voluntary basis and after having expressed fully informed consent, in the first year of the project and consulted all along its lifetime. The procedure and criteria for personal data processing and safeguarding are reported in detail in the D8.1. The documents related to the procedure to recruit research participants submitted as deliverables before the start of the relevant activities will be:

- A declaration of compliance with the respective national legal framework(s) to be carried out by the beneficiary in case of special derogations about the rights of data subjects or the processing of genetic, biometric, and/or health data to be established under the national legislation of the country where the research takes place.

- Clarification of how all the personal data will be processed and the declaration that the personal data collected are relevant and limited to the purposes of the research project (in accordance with the 'data minimization' principle).
- A description of the technical and organizational measures that will be implemented to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subjects/research participants.
- A description of the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorized access to personal data or the equipment used for processing.
- Procedures, in case the participant is unable to provide consent (e.g., children).
- Description of the anonymization/pseudonymization techniques that will be implemented.
- An explicit confirmation that the data used in the project is publicly available and can be freely used for the purposes of the project.
- For the further processing of previously collected personal data, an explicit confirmation that the beneficiary has a lawful basis for the data processing and that the appropriate technical and organizational measures are in place to safeguard the rights of the data subjects.
- The ethical risks related to the data processing activities of the proposal/project must be evaluated. This evaluation must include an opinion on data protection impact assessment that should be conducted under Article 35 General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679.

A summary of the main information related to the procedures and criteria that will be used to process personal data in the activities involving human people in the PLAN'EAT project is reported in Table 5. Effective and understandable informed consent will be used in all LLs explicitly addressing that the personal data will be collected by the organizations having a lawful basis for the data processing and that the appropriate technical and administrative measures are in place to safeguard the rights of the data subjects. In addition to that ethical risks will be monitored and evaluated. This evaluation must include an opinion on data protection impact assessment that should be conducted under Article 35 General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679. Data will be collected according to the minimization principle meaning limiting the data collection to what is strictly necessary for the stated purpose, avoiding gathering excessive or irrelevant information. To ensure participant privacy, several robust anonymization/pseudonymization techniques will be employed such as data masking, aggregation, the combination of individual data points into summary statistics, etc, and any further method to protect individual identities. The duration of the retention period corresponds to the period to keep the personal data which must be only as long as it is necessary to fulfil the purpose/s of PLAN'EAT. The retention period for PLAN'EAT LLs would correspond to the duration of the project as a minimum and would be in line with National/local rules.

Table 5: Informed consent, data minimization principle, anonymization*/pseudonymization** techniques to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subjects/research participants				
Living Lab (LL)	Effective and understandable informed consent	Data minimization principle (adequate, relevant, limited to what is necessary)	Anonymization / Pseudonymization (e.g. key code, code number)	Duration of the retention period
TUM Bayern (DE)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pseudonymization	10 Years
INRAE Auvergne Rhone Alpes (FR)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pseudonymization	Duration of the project (parents, children)
UCD Dublin (IE)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pseudonymization	Duration of the project as a minimum
SLU Sweden (SE)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pseudonymization	Duration of the project (parents, children) as a minimum

JU – Poland (PL)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pseudonymization	Duration of the project as a minimum
ESSRG Budapest (HU)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pseudonymization	Duration of the project
UOC Catalonia (ES)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Anonymization	Duration of the project as a minimum
UNIBO Bologna - Pilastro (IT)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pseudonymization	Duration of the project
HUA Attica (EL)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Anonymization	Duration of the project as a minimum

* 'Anonymized' means that the data has been rendered anonymous in such a way that the data can no longer be identified and excludes any possibility to identify the data subject. Therefore, anonymized data is no longer personal data and thus outside the scope of data protection law.

** 'Pseudonymized' means to divide the data from its direct identifiers so that linkage to a person is only possible with additional information that is held separately. The additional information must be kept separately and securely from processed data to ensure non-attribution. Pseudonymization still makes the data subject identifiable, through the combination of the pseudonym (e.g. key code, code number) with additional identifiers. The time and the effort required to identify the individual as well as the available technologies are decisive for determining whether is possible to identify the data subject from pseudonymized data.

At the time of publication of the present deliverable (M6), the status of the provision of the above-mentioned documents could be summarized as follows:

- The LLs responsible partners of the PLAN'EAT project are putting in place appropriate strategies for personal data confidentially and protection through codification system procedures.
- Data will be used only for scientific aims (e.g., clinical data for subject screening) without any commercial purposes. Security measures for the storage and handling of such data will guarantee the anonymity of the participants. During activities, all participants in the project conform to the current legislation of the respective countries in which research is carried on.
- The LLs of PLAN'EAT will follow the rules and guidelines of the General Data Protection Regulation even in countries where the data protection laws may not be adequate as in the EU following the procedure codified in the Data Management Plan (DMP-D7.4). Privacy policies are clearly explained, and participants must give affirmative consent before his/her data can be used. The processing of participants' personal data is explained in the relevant privacy policies in a clear and transparent manner, and, where necessary, informed consent is asked and collected before the processing takes place. This also applies also for posting/putting a photo of a person on a website; video and other dissemination channels. Files will not be shared for commercial and/or marketing purposes, but only in the strict framework of the PLAN'EAT project and on the continuation of the action initiated together.

3. The Artificial Intelligence (AI) impact and ethics in PLAN'EAT

In the present paragraph the human rights impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI), the criticism of the algorithm design and outcomes of the PLAN'EAT project, and the ethical risks and the mitigation measures related to the AI will be summarised. Details on the impact and ethics of AI in PLAN'EAT are reported in D8.4. AI ethics is based on the fundamental rights enshrined in the EU Treaties, the EU Charter, and international human rights law. Respect for fundamental rights, within a framework of democracy and the rule of law, provides

the most promising foundations for identifying abstract ethical principles and values, which can be operationalized in the context of AI.

In consideration of the PLAN'EAT topic, the following updated definition² of AI is appropriate: *“Artificial intelligence (AI) systems are software (and possibly also hardware) systems designed by humans that, given a complex goal, act in the physical or digital dimension by perceiving their environment through data acquisition, interpreting the collected structured or unstructured data, reasoning on the knowledge, or processing the information, derived from this data and deciding the best action(s) to take to achieve the given goal. AI systems can either use symbolic rules or learn a numeric model, and they can also adapt their behavior by analyzing how the environment is affected by their previous actions”*.

On the basis of the reported definition, the algorithm that will be developed in PLAN'EAT is at the border of AI but not completely classifiable as AI. In fact, in the PLAN'EAT project software based on a complex and comprehensive database with the development of scalable and interrogable algorithms will be created. The algorithms that will be developed in PLAN'EAT will be characterized by clear explicability measures (e.g. traceability, and transparent communication on system capabilities) and could not be classifiable as a 'black box' algorithm. Thus, the PLAN'EAT system of developing recommendations to provide personalized meals and personalized dietary advice as a whole will be designed as respectful of fundamental rights. Explicability will be provided making the process transparent in a context in which the consequences if an output is erroneous or otherwise inaccurate could not impact human rights.

In PLAN'EAT, a specific assessment list aims to help verify the application of each of the 7 key requirements that AI systems should meet in order to be deemed trustworthy³ will be put in place. The above-reported guidelines will be used to report the human rights impact of AI, the criticism of the algorithm design and outcomes of the PLAN'EAT project, and the ethics risks and the mitigation measures related to the AI in PLAN'EAT.

The characteristics of AI in PLAN'EAT will be assessed providing checklists of what needs to be achieved across the period of activity of PLAN'EAT. The PLAN'EAT Ethic Advisor after consulting with WP leaders and interested beneficiary (CERTH) will report on these aspects including the outcome of the evaluation in the Ethic assessments that the PLAN'EAT EA will perform at the end of each reporting period (D8.6, D8.7, D8.8).

Four aspects of AI ethics and the impact of PLAN'EAT will be taken into account:

- 1) The AI PLAN'EAT human rights impact assessment covering the development, deployment, and post-deployment phases, including detailed information on how respect for fundamental human rights and freedoms, will be carried out. AI in PLAN'EAT will be used for the development of dietary personalized recommendations. In the framework of this activity, detrimental aspects of human rights and people's freedom could be identified. However, some specific aspects will be assessed in order to accomplish ALTAI requests.
- 2) Measures will be taken to prevent, avoid, and mitigate potential bias, discrimination, and stigmatization in input data and algorithm design and outcomes in line with the principle of inclusion and diversity that permits the achievement of a trustworthy PLAN'EAT AI.
- 3) AI information to research participants and/or end-users according to the “Transparency” principle⁴ stating that an AI system should have characteristics of explicability and should encompass transparency of relevant elements.
- 4) AI risk assessment and risk mitigation plan based on the principle that a trustworthy AI should minimize and report negative ethical impacts following the value of Accountability⁵.

² https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=60651, accessed on 10 February 2023

³ https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=60419, accessed on 10 February 2023

⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/ai-alliance-consultation/guidelines/1.html#top>, accessed on 10 February 2023

⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/ai-alliance-consultation/guidelines/1.html#top>, accessed on 10 February 2023

Conclusions and Next Steps

- All the LIs responsible started the procedure for ethical clearance requests, 4 out of 9 got the approval; the remaining approvals were achieved before the starting of the activities and reported in Table 20 of the first Technical Report (Part B) provided at M18. Copies of opinions/approvals by ethics committees and/or competent authorities for the research with humans were achieved before the start of the relevant activities, kept on file, and could be provided upon request.
- Informed consent as well as information sheets were prepared by all the LIs responsible and an English template of the informed consent of the PLAN'EAT project was prepared to facilitate to work of the LIs responsible. Copies of the informed consent and information sheets in the local language and English were provided in D8.1.
- As the recruitment of participants will not start at the same time for all LIs, an update on the status of ethical clearances will be provided in the project documents.
- The AI of PLAN'EAT will be created following the EU Guidelines that fixed the requirements that AI systems should meet in order to be deemed trustworthy.
- The human rights impact of AI, the criticism of the algorithm design and outcomes of the PLAN'EAT project, and the ethics risks and the mitigation measures related to the AI will be further assessed and tailored by the PLAN'EAT Ethic Advisor after consulting with WP leaders and interested beneficiaries.